

Homoeopathic Management of Eczema: A Case Report

¹Prof. (Dr.) Harcharanjeet Kaur, ²Dr. Ghazala Parveen, ³Dr. Sankha Subhra Sengupta, ⁴Dr. Tasneem Hashmi

¹PhD. M.D. (Hom), ^{2,3,4} Junior Resident (Department of Repertory)

¹H.O.D. Department of Repertory

^{1,2,3,4}Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru State Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Kanpur, India.

Abstract- Eczema is a common skin condition that causes itchiness, rashes, dry patches and infection. Some people only have small patches of dry skin, but others may experience widespread inflamed skin all over the body. In modern medicines steroids and topical applications are used which suppress the local condition arousing the internal malady and other symptoms which previously existed in latent state side by side. The classical homoeopathic approach makes sure that medicine is prescribed after careful consideration of the whole picture of the person. In this case Kali ars, was given after individualisation to an elderly women with widespread eczema on both hands and legs. She had intense itching, burning and bleeding after scratching. All of her symptoms improved remarkably showing effectiveness of homoeopathic interventions in cases of eczema.

Keywords-Eczema, Homoeopathy, Individualisation, Itching, MONARCH, RADAR, Repertory, Skin eruption.

INTRODUCTION

Eczema is an inflammatory skin condition that causes itchiness, dry skin, rashes, scaly patches, blisters and skin infections. Itchy skin is the most common symptom of eczema. Symptoms of eczema often include: Itch, dryness, sensitive skin; Inflamed, discolored skin; Rough, leathery or scaly skin, appearing as scaly patches; Oozing or crusting; areas of swelling^[1]. Eczema is a relatively common cause of morbidity among the older population. It decreases the quality of life of affected persons and increases the cost of medical care^[2]. The Global Burden of Skin Disease study (2010) estimated that AD affects up to 230 million people worldwide^[3,4]. In this regard, nationwide, systematic studies identifying the disease burden, epidemiology, and challenges in the diagnosis and management of AD in India are lacking^[5].

According to homoeopathic principles, Skin manifestations are reflection of internal systemic diseases so, it should be treated constitutionally to find out the exact cause of skin manifestation rather than suppressing it by local means can lead to more severe systemic problems^[6]. Although there are a wide range of literature available for treatment of eczema in homoeopathy and homoeopathy has shown promising results over the years in cases of skin diseases but not many research study is available. Here a case of eczema is presented which is treated with individualised homoeopathic medicine, showing the effectiveness of homoeopathy in such cases. The case report has been presented as per the HOM-CASE CARE extension guidelines^[7]. Modified Naranjo criteria for Homoeopathy (MONARCH)^[8] has been used for causal attribution.

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 75year Old female, from a poor socio-economic status came to the O.P.D. of Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru State Homoeopathic Medical College, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh on 13th April 2023 with complaints of dry scaly eruptions on dorsum of digits of both hands, over the left shin bone and on both the feet with severe itching, burning in skin and bleeding after scratching. The patient has been suffering from the complaint for 3-4months.

The patient had history of cholecystectomy and asthma and a family history of hypertension and tuberculosis.

The thermal reaction of the patient was very chilly with general amelioration in open air. The appetite of the patient was decreased, the patient had a desire for sour things and warm drinks. Stool was regular once a day, normal in consistency but offensive.

The patient appeared irritated when questioned during case taking. The patient was anxious for her own health, had a desire for company, with fear of being alone, persistent thoughts and very restless especially at night which prevented sleep.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

On examination the patient had very dry, shriveled skin. A mild pallor was present. The blood pressure was 100/70 mm of hg and the pulse rate was 82 beats per minute. The rest of the general physical examination was found to be normal, The patient was conscious and oriented with normal reflexes, soft and non tender abdomen and with audible S1 and S2.

REPERTORISATION

The totality of symptoms for this case includes, Anxiety about her health, fear of being alone, persistent thoughts at night, restlessness at night, stool offensive odor, dry shriveled, wrinkled skin, dry eruptions, itching in skin with burning, desire for sour and warm drinks. After analysis and evaluation of symptoms, this case have more characteristic generals than particular, as adaptability of Repertory of Homoeopathic Materia Medica by J.T.Kent^[9] matches with the case, So the repertory was selected for repertorisation. After repertorisation with Kent's Repertory using RADAR 10^[10] software, giving priority to mental generals

over physical generals and then to particular symptoms, *Kalium arsenicum* was found to cover 11 symptoms scoring 23 marks while *Arsenicum album* covered 10 rubrics getting 26 marks[Figure 1] *Arsenicum album* patients are very fastidious but in this case the patient was not at all fastidious, although loneliness is present in both the remedies but *arsenicum album* manifests this as fear and insecurity whereas *Kalium arsenicum* patient seeks for support from family which was very prominent in this case^[11]. Moreover *Kalium Arsenicum* patients are more chilly and restless more marked compared to *Arsenicum Album* patients which were present in the patient. Although *Kalium Arsenicum* and *Arsenicum album* both got highest grades after repertorisation finally *Kalium Arsenicum* was selected after consultation from different materia medica^[12].

FIGURE-1: Repertorisation chart

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

After individualisation, single homeopathic medicine *Kalium Arsenicum* was selected and prescribed in 200C potency once daily for three days on empty stomach in the morning on 13th April 2023. The patient was advised to take plenty of water and to apply coconut oil externally on the eruptions. The case was followed up till 1st June 2023. The timeline including the follow up details of the patient are given in [Table 1]. Causal attribution was assessed by MONARCH [Table 2]

Table 1: Timeline including follow up of the case

Date	Diet	Exercise	Follow Up	Medicine
27 th April 2023	Followed	Followed	General improvement, better sleep, reduced restlessness at night, significant improvement in skin eruption improvement, itching and burning decreased, no new complaint reported.	Placebo 200CH once daily for 3 days followed by placebo for 15 days.
11 th May 2023	Followed	Followed	No significant improvement, no new complaints appeared	Kalium Arsenicum 200 Once daily for 3 days
18 th May 2023	Followed	Followed	General improvement, no new complaint reported, skin eruption improvement, itching and burning significantly decreased.	Placebo for 15 days.
1 st June 2023	Followed	Followed	General improvement, weakness no longer present, restlessness significantly reduced, no new complaint reported.	Placebo for 15 days.
15 th June 2023	Followed	Followed	No significant improvement, itching and burning slightly increased.	Kalium Arsenicum 200 Once daily for 3 days
1 st March 2023	Followed	Followed	General improvement, skin eruption cured, no itching and burning, better sleep, no restlessness, weakness present.	Placebo for 15 days.

Table 2: MONARCH Inventory

Domains	Yes	No	Not sure or N/A
1. Was there an improvement in the main symptom or condition for which the homeopathic medicine was prescribed?	+2	-1	0

2. Did the clinical improvement occur within a plausible timeframe relative to the drug intake?	+1	-2	0
3. Was there an initial aggravation of symptoms?	+1	0	0
4. Did the effect encompass more than the main symptom or condition (i.e., were other symptoms ultimately improved or changed)?	+1	0	0
5. Did overall well-being improve?	+1	0	
6A Direction of cure: did some symptoms improve in the opposite order of the development of symptoms of the disease?	+1	0	0
6B Direction of cure: did at least two of the following aspects apply to the order of improvement of symptoms: –from organs of more importance to those of less importance? –from deeper to more superficial aspects of the individual? –from the top downwards?	+1	0	0
7. Did “old symptoms” (defined as non-seasonal and non-cyclical symptoms that were previously thought to have resolved) reappear temporarily during the course of improvement?	+1	0	0
8. Are there alternate causes (other than the medicine) that—with a high probability— could have caused the improvement? (Consider known course of disease, other forms of treatment, and other clinically relevant interventions)	-3	+1	0
9. Was the health improvement confirmed by any objective evidence? (e.g., laboratory test, clinical observation, etc.)	+2	0	0
10. Did repeat dosing, if conducted, create similar clinical improvement?	+1	0	0

Total Score: +10

*the numbers in bold font represent the option selected

FIGURE-2 :Before Treatment

FIGURE-3: Before Treatment

FIGURE-4: Before Treatment

FIGURE-5: After Treatment

FIGURE-6: After Treatment

DISCUSSION

As suggested by many studies, homoeopathic interventions prove to be quite beneficial in skin diseases. This is due to the fact that external diseases, according to homoeopathy, occur due to some underlying internal derangement and hence they should be treated internally and not locally. In this case, the patient presented with patchy eruptions on hand and feet. There was severe itching and burning sensation. On scratching, the eruptions bled. The patient's thermal reaction was chilly. Her appetite was low with desire for warm things. Her bowel habits were normal. She had a personal history of asthma and a family history of tuberculosis. She seemed very anxious about her health. Restlessness was very marked due to which she was unable to get a sound sleep. The case was repertorised using Kent's repertory. After analysis of the result, Kali ars was selected and given in 200CH potency. There was marked improvement in her complaints after 3rd visit. The eruptions gradually became diminished. There was relief in itching and burning. Also, there was no bleeding. Not only her physical symptoms but her anxiety was also

controlled. She was much less restless and was getting a better sleep. She was kept on placebo. After few weeks, no further improvement was noticed, instead, her itching was slightly elevated, so the same remedy was repeated. The patient is still being followed up and is improving under treatment. There was marked improvement in the eruptions before [FIGURE 2,3,4] and after treatment [FIGURE 5,6] which can be clearly seen on the images. The MONARCH causality score of this case came out to be 10 [Table-2]. The result here in this case was promising however more controlled studies are needed to be done to establish the efficacy of homeopathic interventions.

CONCLUSION

From this study, it has been observed that homeopathic medicines are effective in cases of eczema when given on the basis of totality of symptoms as per the principles of individualization. The results are found to be statistically significant. Still there is a need for further studies to provide stronger evidence for proving the efficacy of classical homeopathy in cases of eczema.

DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT

The patient was informed about the publication of her data in journal and written consent was taken from the patient.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP

Nil

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

REFERENCES:

1. National Eczema Association. Eczema symptoms & causes [Internet]. National Eczema Association. 2017. Available from: <https://nationaleczema.org/eczema/>
2. Neena V, Asokan N, Jose R, Sarin A. Prevalence of eczema among older persons: A population-based cross-sectional study. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 2023;89:426-30.
3. Hay RJ, Johns NE, Williams HC, et al. The global burden of skin disease in 2010: an analysis of the prevalence and impact of skin conditions. *J Invest Dermatol*. 2014;134(6):1527–1534. doi:10.1038/jid.2013.446
4. Laughter MR, Maymone MBC, Mashayekhi S, et al. The global burden of atopic dermatitis: lessons from the Global Burden of Disease Study 1990–2017*. *Br J Dermatol*. 2021;184(2):304–309. doi:10.1111/bjd.19580
5. Rajagopalan M, Chitkara AJ, Dalwai S, De A, Gulati R, Mukherjee S, Mutalik S, Sharma N, Shenoi S, Vaidya P, Tilak A, Adhav C. Burden of Disease, Unmet Needs in the Diagnosis and Management of Atopic Dermatitis: An Indian Expert Consensus. *Clin Cosmet Investig Dermatol*. 2021;14:1755-1765 <https://doi.org/10.2147/CCID.S327593>
6. Sharma A, Akhtar SM. Sequel of dermatological suppression. *IJHS* 2022; 6(2): 286-288, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33545/26164485.2022.v6.i2e.572>
7. Van Haselen RA. Homeopathic clinical case reports: Development of a supplement (HOM-CASE) to the CARE clinical case reporting guideline. *Complement Ther Med* 2016;25:78-85
8. Lamba CD, Gupta VK, van Haselen R, Rutten L, Mahajan N, Molla AM, et al. Evaluation of the modified Naranjo criteria for assessing causal attribution of clinical outcome to homeopathic intervention as presented in case reports. *Homeopathy* 2020;109:191-7
9. Kent JT. *Repertory of Homoeopathic Materia Medica*. New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers Pvt Ltd.; 2012.
10. RADAR Computer Programme. Belgium: Version 10 Developed by Archibel Homoeopathic Software Company; 2009
11. Boericke W. *New Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica with Repertory*. 3rd ed. B. Jain Publishers Pvt Ltd.; 2012.
12. Hering C. *The Guiding Symptoms of Our Materia Medica*. Reprinted., Vol. VIII. New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers (P) Ltd.; 2005